

The forgotten half: Men's influence over cookstove adoption decisions in Northern Kenya

Caroline A. Ochieng^{a,b,*}, Una Murray^{a,c}, John Owuor^d, Charles Spillane^a

^a Ryan Institute, National University of Ireland Galway, University Road, Galway H91 REW4, Ireland

^b Energy Sector Management Assistance Program, The World Bank, 1818 H Street, NW., Washington DC 20433, USA

^c MSc Climate Change, Agriculture and Food Security Program (MScCCAFS), National University of Ireland Galway, University Road, Galway H91 REW4, Ireland

^d Swedish Program for ICT in Developing Countries, Borgarfjordsgatan 12, 164 55 Kista, Stockholm, Sweden

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ABSTRACT

Current research on cleaner cookstoves (CCS) is focused primarily on women, thus removing men from the cookstove adoption equation despite their decision making role in households. Very little is understood about what would motivate men to purchase CCS, and whether such motivations are key factors that influence a household's decision to acquire CCS. There is a paucity of comparative analyses of men and women perspectives on this topic. This study adopted a qualitative approach to gain a first-hand perspective of men on this issue, and to compare findings with that of women in order to identify any similarities and gaps that could shape the eventual outcome of acquisition of a CCS. Contrary to published literature of women's perception of men as being naïve to the challenges associated with traditional cookstoves, we find men in our study to be highly aware of such challenges, having experienced them as child-cooks while growing up. However, this awareness does not translate into an interest in purchasing CCS. While women expressed a strong desire for CCS, men who wield power over decisions to acquire CCS viewed them as status symbols, unnecessary and unattainable. This gender imbalance in motivation and power forecloses opportunities for household adoption of CCS. We recommend that programs should equally target men with CCS messaging, bundle cookstoves with other products that men value, and take advantage of women's groups as a source of collective bargaining power for women in the acquisition of CCS.

1. Introduction

1.1. Differential gender impacts of cookstove interventions

It is well established that the clean cooking sector has differential impacts on women and men, largely based on their gender roles. According to the International Energy Agency (IEA), the way energy is accessed and used is not neutral in its impact, with women experiencing most of the negative impacts of lack of energy access [1]. Women and girls are reported to experience significantly higher exposure to household air pollution than men [2,3], given their close proximity to household fires during high pollution episodes. Women and girls are also disproportionately affected by the time burden of biomass dependence because of the time they spend engaged in collecting fuelwood and cooking [2,4]. Other impacts that are disproportionately borne by women and girls include physiological injuries from transporting heavy

and large quantities of fuel [5]; risk of accidents and hazards such as burns, fires, blunt trauma and explosions from cooking and heating appliances [6]; and risk of intimate partner violence from delayed or poorly cooked food and disagreements over cooking and heating expenditures [7,8].

Based on the above linkages, cookstove interventions comprising of technologies that make solid fuels burn in a cleaner manner, and alternative modern fuels (liquefied petroleum gas, electricity, biogas, and ethanol) are widely expected to have more benefits for women than men [1]. For brevity, we use the terminology cleaner cookstove (CCS) throughout this paper to refer to all the above interventions, unless stated otherwise. To date very few studies have been conducted on gender differentiated impacts of CCS interventions. The majority of studies are focussed on measurements and interviews with women, who generally self-report benefits in areas such as health improvement, fuel use reduction, cleanliness and faster cooking [9–11]. In a few studies,

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: caroline.ochieng@nuigalway.ie (C.A. Ochieng).

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men's perception of the benefits are captured through the women. One study [12] provides anecdotal findings on men's perception (who were not sampled as study participants); indicating that they were indifferent about the benefits of LPG in smoke reduction, although they appreciated the benefits of cooking speed that enabled them to have prompt meals before and after work. The dearth of studies on the benefits of interventions from the men's perspective is an evidence gap that others have also noted [2,13].

1.2. Gender norms in household decision making

While it is acknowledged that women are disproportionately affected by lack of energy access, there is a lack of clarity on how to account for this in the design of CCS interventions. Acknowledging that gender roles usually dictate that women are involved in cooking and are the ultimate users of cookstove innovations, the focus of cookstove interventions is frequently on women. However, this has proven inadequate to facilitate CCS adoption and its benefits, with several studies [9,14–18] across various settings reporting that men had the ultimate decision making power when it came to acquisition of cookstoves. Other studies also demonstrate the drivers of adoption of innovations in household energy [10,19–22] as well as in other sectors such as sanitation [23,24], agriculture [25] and healthcare [26] vary by gender.

Men's acceptance or resistance to cookstove interventions may not relate to the intervention itself; but to the social, physical, cultural and economic realities in which they live [27]. Person et al [9] for instance reports that women explained during interviews that their husbands did not want them to create a vent necessary for the stove by cutting a hole in their wall, which deterred adoption and proper use of the stove. Sesan [27] finds that the barrier to CCS adoption in rural Kenya was not a direct resistance of men to the technology but the inability to make the major investment of an outdoor kitchen that was necessary for housing the new (low cost) cookstove. Barnes et al [28] report that a CCS in India required regular chimney cleaning that entailed climbing the roof; which was physically challenging to the women, and a task the men did not want to perform. In rural Mexico, Catalán-Vázquez et al [17] finds that men did not welcome the idea of other men entering their homes while the wives were alone to construct and maintain cookstoves, which deterred the uptake.

The examples above demonstrate how introducing an innovation like a cleaner cookstove can radically disrupt the existing gender norms. Programs that focus on women alone ignore the capacity of women to initiate actions and determine the wide reaching outcomes [29] of interventions like CCS. This however should not imply that men should be the target of such interventions. Muneer [30] provides a case study of a program in Sudan that promoted a stove to men instead of women, based on a heuristic assumption that in such patriarchal societies men are the decision-makers. The lack of success of the program is partly explained by the fact that women in that setting were the decision makers on adoption of ICS. An equally important consideration is the different levels of power associated with different gender roles when it comes to decision making. In the case of Sudan, women had the power on decisions relating to the kitchen, but it was limited to very meagre proportion of the household's financial resources. Studies in other settings have reported similar findings [9,31]. In such contexts, highly priced cooking solutions that are above the small budgets that women control would therefore not be attainable without the husband's involvement. Where the costs are low enough and within the share of expenditure that women can control, they can have the power to make independent purchase decisions as shown by some studies [9,32].

It is also important to consider intra-gender differences in decision-making power, to help to isolate groups that may remain excluded or that require to be specially targeted when designing gender responsive CCS programs. In rural Mexico, 70% of the women interviewed reported that they did not bear the responsibility of fuelwood collection, a role that was performed by their husbands or other male members of the

family [31]. In this society, single women were reported to be at a great disadvantage, having to perform this traditionally male role by themselves. With increasing urbanization, gender relations may also be changing, not just between the sexes but also amongst them. In many parts of urban Africa where women are more engaged in salaried employment, women of lower socio-economic status perform the cooking role and are the ones who experience directly the negative impacts of traditional cooking, while having no power to make the decision to change. In rural Kenya, some women are reported to have had to negotiate stove acquisition with other women in the extended family such as co-wife (the first wife) and mother-in-law, who wielded more power. Where such negotiations were successful, those women would intercede for them to be allocated funds by their husbands. These intra-gender power differences is supported by other literature [26].

1.3. Analyzing decision making through a gender lens

In analyzing gender roles in decision making, many researchers in the past generally adopted the *unitary approach* in which the individual behavior model was simply applied to the household. While this model has been credited for bringing about the recognition that the impact of interventions differ depending on which member of the household is targeted, it has since been widely discredited for amongst other limitations, lacking an empirical basis, and inadvertently reinforcing women's traditional gender roles as caregivers and men as producers (thereby limiting women's agency) [33–35]. The critics of this model have argued that even if household members do not completely pool resources, the fact that people form households (as characterized by shared ownership of resources, joint production, raising family and sharing consumption) is an indicator that there are gains to jointness in gender and family dynamics. Households consist of complex social relations that exist between women themselves, and between women and men in a household [36]. Understanding both individual roles within households and the levels of cooperation, including joint decision-making and ownership of resources, is thus essential to analysis of households.

How to reach an improved understanding of such gender roles and relations is of great importance. While there is limited literature to draw on from the energy sector there is a body of evidence from the agriculture sector (reviewed recently by Doss and Quinsmbing, [33]) showing that when the same questions are posed to multiple people within the household, the responses differ systematically by gender. In rural Tanzania, husbands and wives are reported to have disagreed on who had the authority over key farming, family, and livelihood decisions [37]. In Ecuador [38] perception on agricultural decision-making was found to differ between men and women, with men reporting lower levels of women's participation compared to their wives. Similarly in Kyrgyzstan [39] difference in responses between husbands and wives regarding women's participation in major economic decisions were reported, with wives more likely than husbands to indicate that wives participate in decision making.

There is limited literature on gender differences in preferences and uptake of cookstove interventions, and even fewer that seek to capture this from the male perspective. The few studies available focus on women's perspectives, reflecting the general practice of women as the target of such interventions. Nonetheless those studies offer some useful insights on intra-household decision making on adoption of cookstoves. Miller and Mobarak [32] performed an experiment on stove demand in Bangladesh where they offered the choice of stoves with different attributes separately to women and men in randomly selected households. They report stark differences in choices made by women and men. When stoves were offered for free, women exhibited a stronger preference for them and were more likely to adopt them than men. But when a small price was charged for the stoves, their preferences were reduced. Differences were also observed between women and men on the type of cookstoves to adopt, while amongst the women there were significant

differences in the choice they made by education, age and an index of empowerment. Similar results for men are not provided by that study. In India, Jeuland and colleagues [40,41] performed a similar experiment that included both men and women. Men were however underrepresented in the sample (27%) and women are reported to have placed bids on behalf of their husbands due to men's frequent unavailability; a limitation the authors acknowledge. The study did not disaggregate their findings by gender. The under-representation of men is also seen in a study in Nigeria [42] that surveyed households to get their perspective on stove preferences and inter household decision-making, based on a sample of 2 men and 19 women.

If indeed systematic differences exist in male and female perspectives on intra-household decision making, and men are the primary decision makers in the households, then a critical part of the cookstove adoption equation is missing and not being considered by current CCS interventions. This is a gap that other authors have also identified, specifically calling for engagement of men, youth and other family members in cookstove adoption studies [13]. There are increasing calls for improvement in design, rigor and validity in the energy sector research [43–46]. Meaningful engagement of men in cookstove studies should be considered among the defining features of such rigor.

1.4. Aim of study

The current study sought to understand the roles of women and men in decision making on the adoption of cleaner cookstoves. There is no commonly accepted definition of cookstove adoption, with various studies applying different interpretations. Any interpretation should however consider adoption as a process that begins with acceptance of the stoves, without which no stove program can achieve its goals [47]. The definition we adopt in this paper is aligned with the concept of “user journeys” proposed by Jürisoo et al [48] and focuses on events and decision points that build up to the milestone of purchasing a cookstove. These events include (after the initial point of awareness of the stove) seeing the stove as desirable, availability of the stove for purchase, and being able to afford to purchase the stove or obtain financing for it [48]. Drawing on interviews with men and women from both rural and urban settings in Kenya, the study sought gender-differentiated perspectives on intra-household decision making on stove adoption, overcoming limitations of previous research where men's perspectives are either ignored or voiced by women. The study adds to the limited literature available on the influence of gender on the adoption of cookstoves, and on the role of men in this process in particular, based on their first-hand accounts. The study is expected to inform further research as well as policy on the design of gender responsive interventions in the clean cooking sector.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Setting

The study draws on a case study in West Pokot County in Northern Kenya. West Pokot is among the 16 counties that are defined as ‘marginalized areas’ by the Kenyan Commission on Revenue Allocation (CRA). The CRA defines these as “communities that have been excluded from social and economic life of Kenya for different reasons” and “geographic locations (county or sub-county) where significant populations of underserved communities live” [49]. A World Bank financed program, the Kenya Off-grid Solar Access Project (KOSAP) is currently underway in these counties, with the goal of scaling up access to modern energy. The program is promoting both off-grid solar and clean cookstoves by supporting the creation of a sustainable market for the products and services. The study site was purposively selected to generate data that can inform the design of this program, which is being implemented in a phased approach.

According to a World Bank survey conducted in these counties in 2018 [50] biomass is the predominant cooking fuel, used by 94.3% of

the population as a primary fuel. Firewood is the most common fuel for rural households, while charcoal is the most predominant fuel for urban residents. Majority of households (85%) in the underserved counties reported using biomass on traditional cookstoves, significantly higher than 62.8% proportions reported for the rest of the country. Less than 4% of households in the 14 under-served counties used clean fuel stoves, compared to 18% in the rest of Kenya. However the households in these regions were more likely to use the traditional fuels on improved wood stoves.

The use of multiple cookstoves and fuels that often includes a combination of traditional and cleaner cookstoves (stacking) is a common occurrence in Kenya [50–52]. Stacking rates and patterns also vary between rural and urban areas. The World Bank study reports rates of stacking as 35% for urban households and 28% for rural households.

Amongst the constraints of acquiring cleaner cookstoves is affordability [50,51]. Almost three-fourths (78%) of Kenyan households, mostly in urban areas are reported to allocate more than 5% of their household expenditures on cooking. Adopting CCS could reduce fuel expenditures, but low-income household face liquidity constraints that deter these purchases. Some cookstove programs have responded to this need by including financing options in their program designs.

2.2. Design

A qualitative study design based on grounded theory [53] was used to gain an in-depth insight into the differences between men and women in decision making, with specific reference to clean cookstoves. In essence, this meant that the analysis and development of this understanding evolved with repeated iterations of data collection and analysis. There was no preconceived theory on gender influence on intra-household decision making.

2.3. Participants

Twenty-three married couples were recruited for this study using theoretical sampling. Theoretical sampling [54,55] is a purposive method that seeks participants most relevant to the developing theory (relevant information sources rather than individuals). Theoretical sampling does not seek representation of the general population. Instead it focuses on seeking further information that builds on the emerging theory. The process of recruitment, data collection and analysis went on iteratively until data saturation was achieved, with each additional data building on the emergent theory.

Participants were recruited by research assistants residing in those communities, who made initial contact with either the man or woman responsible for the household at the time of the visit. Guided by the emerging theory, participants were selected on the basis of their gender, area of residence, experience with different cooking technologies and family composition. After recruitment of the index participant, he/she was requested to invite their spouse to participate in the study. Where both the man and woman were present, they were recruited at the same time; but as individual participants. Snowballing technique was used to identify more participants who were relevant to the emergent theory. The iterative process of recruitment, data collection and analysis went on until the researcher was contented that no more new insights were emerging from the additional data to warrant further sampling and recruitments.

2.4. Data collection

Data was collected through 6 Focus Group Discussions, each made up of between 5 and 8 participants. The FGDs took place approximately one week apart to allow time for data analysis and sampling of participants. Separate discussions were held with the men and women. The interviewers made it clear to participants that the views they expressed would be treated confidentially. Participants were also urged not to

discuss responses with their spouses until they had both participated in the interviews, although the research team made no attempt to enforce this.

The FGDs were conducted in both Swahili and Pokot, the locally spoken languages. The FGDs were conducted by a male and a female research assistant who are familiar with the study setting, and moderated by the Principal Investigator (CAO) who is also conversant in Swahili and the sociocultural context. The design of the data collection tools (FGD guides) and their piloting was led by CAO, who trained the local researchers in their administration. The FGDs took place in local convening venues (a rural church and a conference centre) that could be easily accessed by participants. Refreshments were provided to participants before commencement of the discussions which lasted for about one hour. Participants also received a transport reimbursement of Ksh. 200 (USD 2).

All the FGDs were audio-recorded with the respondents' consent. These were complemented with notes taking on key issues that emerged during the discussions.

2.5. Data analysis

Analysis of the FGD findings and other qualitative results was through transcript and notes based thematic analysis which took place immediately after an FGD. Data analysis started with familiarization through listening to the audio tapes several times, followed by verbatim transcription of each interview and FGD audio tape. The transcripts were then re-read repeatedly, noting down any points that stood out from the initial readings.

Data analysis was done using the three-step iterative coding process based on constant comparison of data. New data were continuously collected through new cases (theoretical sampling as explained above) which were more likely to contribute to the development of the evolving theory. The three coding processes used were open coding, axial coding and selective coding [53]. Coding involved assigning general concepts to specific incidences in the data for example 'male decisions' in cookstove purchase, which was further developed into gender-based decisions. The three coding processes were not carried out in a linear manner but rather in iterative overlapping manner in adherence to grounded theory approach.

Open coding focused on conceptualisation and categorisation of data by breaking down the data into smallest possible analytical parts to understand the key idea behind each part, thereby assigning it a code to describe it. The process involved asking of the data questions such as what is being said, who is saying it and what are their roles, how are they involved with the issue, why, and how long. The analysis thus took into account differences in gender, but also other variables, such as being male from a particular social group, or being a highly educated female from a particular location (urban versus rural). Open coding was then followed by axial coding which explored the relationships between the concepts and categories developed through open coding. Finally, selective coding was done to integrate different categories developed and linked together through axial coding into meaningful themes/theory.

2.6. Ethics

The study was granted ethical approval by the National University of Ireland Galway Ethics Committee, and Strathmore University Ethics Committee (Reference Number SU-IERC0551/19). As per the requirements of the ethics committee, the identity of the participants is anonymized, and detailed information that could lead to identification of participants is omitted from the paper.

3. Results

3.1. Characteristics of respondents

The mean age of female participants was 29 years, and 32 years for men. Female participants ranged in age from 18 to 45, and men from 22 to 60 years of age. There was no significant difference in age between urban and rural residents. Men had generally higher education levels than women and had more regular income sources. The primary occupation for most rural residents (both men and women) was farming, which was often combined with other activities such as charcoal burning, casual labour (mainly farm level) and small businesses. A few participants had diverse regular income sources including pension and remittances. In contrast, the common occupation in urban areas was casual labour or self-employment, as well as full-time salaried employment. With the exception of 2 couples who stated they belonged to the Islamic faith; the remainder stated they were of Christian faith. Home maker as a primary occupation was only reported by women.

The main stove used by rural participants was the traditional three-stone stove. Over half the households stacked it with charcoal stoves or with improved wood stoves (rocket mud stove). In contrast, urban respondents were mainly using charcoal stoves; nearly all of them having the traditional or basic improved brand that does not meet the technical parameters of a clean cookstove. Half of urban participants stacked the charcoal stoves with gas stoves.

Because the study is based on a purposive sample, the demographic profiles and stove ownership patterns do not reflect what exists in the general population.

Table 1 below shows the demographic characteristics of participants that were linked to decision making on CCS adoption. Classifications such as highly educated housewives or stay at home husbands were not observed in the sample.

3.2. Limitations of traditional cookstoves are perceived by both men and women, but men do not see interventions as necessary

Men demonstrated a high awareness of the challenges posed by traditional cookstoves and were able to provide elaborate details on some impacts (e.g. carbon monoxide toxicity that can occur from using charcoal stoves indoors). All of the men narrated personal experiences of using traditional stoves when they were young, having been introduced to them by their parents or guardians. They reported that their roles growing up included fetching firewood, tending the fire as their first initiation to cooking, and gradually being assigned to prepare full family meals. Some men also reported they had continued to cook in their bachelorhood, although most in the rural area had transitioned from their parent's home to marriage. Apart from this personal experience they had the second-hand experience from observing cooking in their households, and their parents when they visited them back home (for men living in urban areas). Men were therefore not ignorant of the issues of cooking smoke, difficulty in lighting and maintaining heat on the

Table 1
Categories of research participants.

Categories	Identifier		Total
	Rural	Urban	
Men			
High or mid-level education, salaried	A1-1	A2-1	6
High or mid-level education, casual or self-employed	A1-2	A2-2	5
Low education, salaried	A1-3	A2-3	3
Low education, casual or self-employed	A1-4	A2-4	9
Women			
High or mid-level education, salaried	B1-1	B2-1	5
High or mid-level education, casual or self-employed	B1-2	B2-2	4
Low education, casual or self-employed	B1-4	B2-4	10
Low education, housewife	B1-5	B2-5	4
Total	28	18	46

stoves, inability to regulate the cooking, uncleanliness and low cooking speed; and recounted all these challenges during interviews.

In their current status as husbands however, they were not taking part in any fuel harvesting or cooking activities, except on rare occasions such as when their wife was sick or had given birth. These were very short episodes of less than one week. On occasions where the woman was unable to cook for an extended period of time a solution would be found, such as bringing over female relatives, including mothers, to offer support. Such arrangements were often made by the women, who recounted that cooking was their responsibility and not a man's. One man reported that for the periods the wife could not cook he would buy food from local hotel, while another reported getting a second wife.

Marriage therefore marked a permanent transition for men away from cooking, and from direct experience of physically fetching fuel and using traditional cookstoves. Rarely was it reported that a man would be in the kitchen while cooking was taking place, even for urban residents who lived in small house units. In these settings men were reported to be out working most of the time and home in time for meals. When asked if there ever were conversations as a couple related to cooking fuels and stove, very few women and men gave an affirmative response; and none were able to recount details of such conversations. The constant narrative coming from both men and women was that issues of kitchen and cooking were the woman's domain.

Despite the acknowledgement of problems associated with use of traditional cookstoves by men, tackling such problems did not come up as a priority, or even a necessity. This was in stark contrast to the women's narrative of wanting to have a solution to these problems and having taken some steps to try to resolve them. Men perceived women as being used to the experience, and being experts in managing those challenges.

As you know this traditional (charcoal) stove has no reverse gear (figurative on no heat control). But my wife, she knows how to manage it very well. She plans her cooking and knows how to regulate the heat and gets everything done without burning food or wasting fuel – A2-4.

Similar views on women as “fire experts” came out strongly across various male interviews. For instance, in an interview with urban men who no longer cooked with traditional open fire, one acknowledged that his wife would not be able to cook on that kind of stove, but his mother back home could because she had the expertise, was used to it, and therefore would in his view not require him to purchase gas for her even though he could afford to.

Concurrent with these views, most of the men interviewed did not express any desire to acquire CCS. Furthermore, they viewed adoption of CCS as a major life transition, associating it with a rise in living standards and something not within their reach. This view was especially common among men with lower socio-economic status. A woman wishing for a gas stove was perceived as wanting to move to a higher living standard, and refusing to accept the reality of her life. This narrative emerged strongly in several independent FGDs with men.

I am aware of clean cookstoves but am not thinking of buying one. We have fuelwood here; it really depends on your living standard, those gas and clean cookstoves are just a dream – A1-3.

This gas or cookstoves, maybe it is Ksh 20,000 (USD 200) that could buy a cow. You know, it is not a must to have some things in life... You know in your life what is in your level. I eat well in my house, we have never gone hungry, so starting to think gas, something that could cost Ksh. 20,000 or jiko okoa (an ICS brand) costing Ksh. 5000, one would rather buy a goat – A1-1.

For rural residents, the existence of free fuelwood compounded the difficulty in attaching value to gas. Even men in urban households where fuel had to be purchased perceived gas a status symbol that was not worth investing in.

While men perceived CCS as out of reach and unnecessary, women expressed a high regard for them, citing several ways it could benefit them. Women saw cooking with CCS and gas as attainable, and isolated from a rise in socio-economic status. While some had resigned themselves to never being able to acquire them, particularly those who had no independent income source, a majority expressed aspirations for CCS, despite awareness that their spouses did not share this view.

I plan to buy gas, so that I can use it to prepare food quickly if in a hurry, and not to have to wake up too early to be able to get breakfast ready for my children before school...I have asked around and it is not expensive to use. One refill can last for 2 or 3 months if am not using it a lot...with gas I do not have to constantly struggle with wood or charcoal and managing the fire, I look for small money here and there, refill it and that's it! - B2-5

Some noted they had informed their spouses of the intention to acquire those stoves in future, but with no expectation that they would be receiving any financial support from them. One participant observed that since she had no way of getting the stove on her own, and really wanted one, she had to keep making her case with the husband.

As women we suffer. We have to defend ourselves because we are the ones in the kitchen, otherwise we will continue to suffer. Therefore, I must table the issue of stove [CCS] with my husband, otherwise he will never consider it – B1-5.

3.3. Men are decision makers on all major expenditures, including acquisition of CCS

The narrative of single decision making on household expenditure existed, but was not common. Where this was the case, men had the decision making authority.

As the homeowner I decide on all expenditures: hospital, fees, food it is me. I make weekly budget for food, buy it and bring it home. My wife then ensures that what I have bought lasts for at least the one week I budgeted. When it is finished, she tells me, and I again prepare a budget for the following week – A2-1

Where family stands, as my friend [co-participant] here has said, everything is the man. As a man you must know how to balance your children's diet, such as how often they should eat rice, meat, fruits. Cooking is the wife but how children will eat is the man – A2-2

I am everything. I make the decisions. To upgrade how we cook it will be me, if I don't want gas it will not come – A1-1

The person with decision making authority in this house is Mzee [husband]. No using money “ovyo ovyo” [recklessly] as you wish. He will buy a stock of maize and bring it home, I do not need to know how much he has bought, I just use it and when it is finished, he brings more. Fees he pays, and everything else. Where we live women are forbidden to have money. Wazee control everything – B2-5.

A narrative of joint decision making was however more common. There was a clear division of decision-making power regarding certain household expenditures, with women and men wielding different power levels over expenditures. Yet, within the joint decision-making, men clearly wielded more power. Women had autonomy only when it came to decisions around the kitchen, and only where such expenses were below a certain threshold. Men on the other hand had power over decisions on large expenses (such as school fees, housing and hospital costs).

My wife is responsible for decisions around food and kitchen. She says what we need, and I organize myself on how to acquire them. When it comes to school fees, hospital then it is me - A2-3.

As Christians we've been taught to sit together and make decisions jointly, which we do. But on meals it's the wife who decides, she is the one who spends time in the kitchen and knows what the children's and the family needs are. She decides on what meals and I buy, or we help each other to buy. But for expenditures like school fees and hospital it is both of us – A1-1.

We both make decisions. There are things I can do, things I can't do, some we help each other. Small things such as food I am responsible for. When I do not have money, I ask him for it – B2-2.

When Mzee [husband] is present he would ask "what will you people eat today?", and he provides the money for buying it. But when he is absent it is me who makes the decision. Hospital we discuss, school fees we discuss, food only when he is present, he says what he wants to eat – B1-4.

As can be seen above, different interpretations are applied to joint decision-making. While there were instances where women had autonomy over certain decisions, in others they were simply informed of the decisions, and that would be interpreted as joint decision-making. Part of these variations were dependent on whether the man was a sole income earner or there was joint income from the spouses, whether the couple lived together or not, their level of earnings and socio-physical setting. Having own income allowed some women to make their choices prioritised. Women who lived apart from their husbands reported having more autonomy over decisions, as they would be in control of the household budget during those periods they lived apart. Men living in urban areas were also more likely to report joint decision making than those who lived in rural areas, although this could also be explained by the fact that women in urban areas had relatively higher income than their rural counterparts.

The higher power wielded by men emerges clearly in situations where a consensus is not reached on what is required for the household. Men would then have the final decision.

If we discuss and the item is not really needed then she will have to cater for it, I will not pay a cent! – A1-2

When she gives me the list of food items she wants bought I must also prioritize. If my earnings for that period is low and she wants me to buy flour, cooking oil and royco (a spice) then I buy the other items but leave out royco – A2-1

Mzee must be up, I am below him, if I see something I like, I must say "I've seen something there that is appealing, what do you think about us buying it?". Then we go to see it. I have to agree with him because he is up – B2-4

Also noted in some narratives is the man conferring the decision-making power to the woman;

There are things mama [a wife] decides, and those she can't decide. Big things it is me. Small things like jiko [cookstove] are her responsibility. I have left for her those small things. Gas will be me because it is something big. – A1-4.

In situations where women had their own regular income, they would contribute to food costs and other households expenditures. Generally however major expenses remained the men's responsibility (although this could be a reflection of the study sample; there were no women earning more than their husbands). One man observed that as an African man, it would be considered a curse if he were to be financially dependent on the woman.

While cookstoves were generally considered a large expense, most men were opposed to investing in them. Some men however reported that they did not see a problem in women making those purchases on their own.

If she has ability and willing to purchase one that is ok, because on decisions on jiko [cookstove] it is the woman who has the opinion, not me. She is the one with the knowledge that children are eating

late, or the negative experience of cooking outdoor while it rains, or that a child cannot be prepared for tea in the morning before going to school. She therefore makes the decision – A1-1

Getting gas was my own decision. Because I saw the old stove was giving me losses. I light jiko, I've finished cooking, but the fire still remains and there's nothing am cooking with it. So am wasting charcoal, and economy is difficult. Gas after I use it, I simply turn it off – B2-1

I decided on my own to purchase gas. At times I come late from work, hungry, and need food to be ready quickly. The gas stove cooks fast. In the morning it helps me a lot in quickly preparing breakfast for children before they go to school and allows me to arrive at work on time – B2-2.

On the contrary, some women narrated that even from their own earnings or savings, they lacked the power to make independent decisions and had no control over their finances.

Decision on money is Baba [husband]. As women, we do not have our own money. Even when you go and do casual labour or burn some charcoal and sell he asks "where is your Ksh. 300 (USD 3) you received, use it to buy maize". It is hard for us to have any money, they take it away from us. Even hospital that he should be paying for, if he knows I have some money he says "pay with your money". It is a very difficult life – B1-4.

Mzee knows I do not belong to a group [women's group], so he has to know about the source of money for the stove, otherwise I will be divorced if a stove comes here and he isn't aware of how it was acquired. He must know – B1-5.

This echoes the assertion by a male participant that "if I don't want gas it will not come here". Given the low value attributed to clean cookstoves by men, it is clear that even women who have their own income source that they would wish to allocate towards purchasing a cookstove might still be unable to exercise their choice.

3.4. Men's power on decision making forecloses the possibility of acquiring cookstoves on credit

As noted earlier, most men in this study perceived CCS as unattainable. Women on the other hand expressed affordability as their constraint to acquiring CCS. The main challenge they reported was the high upfront cost of the stoves, which pushed the products above the expenditure threshold they had control over and into the men's domain. Perception on savings and credit as a means of overcoming the high upfront cost was therefore explored in the interviews.

While several women reported they were in the process of, or were planning to start making savings that would enable them to one day acquire the stoves, they reported difficulties with this approach. They narrated how they would save for the stoves, but other priorities would come up and the money would be reallocated, putting them right back to where they had started. They were thus stuck in the cycle of saving, spending on other urgent (or higher) priorities, and starting all over again with the same outcome.

I had planned to acquire gas last year. I have been saving money little by little. But even if you save another plan comes and you find you have spent the money. I hope this time I will be able to use my savings for it - B1-1.

The problem is that you cannot get the jiko with half the money, you must have it all. You save, but something comes up that you buy, and you are back to zero – B1-2.

Consequently, the possibility of credit and instalment payments, when raised with the women, was highly regarded. However, when the same option was raised with men, it was considered out of the question. Similar to household expenditures, decisions on credit facilities were controlled by men. Men observed that their wives would not take credit

without their permission. While women reported they had access to credit facilities, they similarly observed they would not take any credit without first discussing and getting the approval from their husbands. The findings mirror those on men's control over household expenditure.

Nothing will happen in our house without discussion. Something like this that drags for long [payment period] she cannot commit to before we discuss. If something very small, then yes – A1-1

Any issue of credit we have to discuss first, so that if we are stuck, we are stuck together. If she takes it on her own, she will suffer [the repayment] alone – A2-3

This was a recurrent view that was also reported by women i.e. "suffering on their own" should they take credit decisions without consultation.

It is easy to be given loan, you go ask they give you but you must know how you will repay it. Hence I must discuss with my husband what I want to do with the loan, and how it will benefit us so that when the time for repayment comes he can support me – B2-4

I cannot take a stove on credit even if there was such an offer. You can be given but you cannot have money for repaying when it is needed – B1-2

I can't take credit. Mzee doesn't want anything to do with loans, so who will repay? – B2-5

While the responses imply that the central issue is consultation, from the responses it was also clear what the outcome of any such consultation would be. Men observed that they would never take, or support credit being taken for a cookstove. Compared to other decisions where there were a few differing perspectives amongst men, the view against taking stoves on credit was near unanimous, with men perceiving it as wanting to live beyond one's means. Loans and credits, according to them, were for productive assets. Some stated that it would block the opportunity of taking credit for more valued items.

The way I was taught, I can never take loan for something that does not generate income. For a goat I can take a loan, it will give birth to another goat, but jiko? Let it stay until I have money to buy one – A1-1.

I would not take a stove to pay for it in instalments, I have other things coming up that would be blocked if I tie myself to paying for a cookstove – A2-1

The narrative of a woman's refusal to accept her social status emerged much more strongly here, with others going as far as saying it would be an indication of a woman not caring for the household's economy and future. This corresponds to the view that credits on stoves would block opportunities for acquiring the same for productive assets and other priorities. Taken jointly with the finding that men perceive CCS as unnecessary and status symbols, a woman expressing a desire to acquire one on credit would not only fail to get the outcome she wishes for, but would also leave a negative impression of rejecting her social status (and by extension the husband as the bread winner), being extravagant and unwise.

While unanimously opposed to credit facilities for cookstoves, some men reported they had taken loans for Solar Home Systems, which suggests they were not restricting credit to productive assets like livestock. Unlike these other products where past experience would inform the current perception on credit, for cookstoves, it was simply considered out of the question.

Once I got myself in such type of [credit] situation, with a type of Dlight solar product that doesn't even provide much energy. And the money I paid? One year plus of deductions which in the end totalled Ksh. 18000. For something small that you can even get for Ksh. 5000 if paying directly. Never again!" – A1-3.

The only situation where men would support taking of credit for a

cookstove was if the woman could afford to pay for it herself, or if the credit was of very low value. This does not however remove the negative perception attached to such actions. Furthermore, as already noted earlier, CCS were considered a large expense (Ksh.5000 minimum); the very reason why women could not acquire them without the man's permission.

The recurrent men's narrative of a woman wishing for a stove wanting to live beyond her means is not supported by other findings of this study. Women owning gas were not of high socio-economic status, and the stove was not an easy acquisition. They narrated the struggle and perseverance that it took them to acquire it.

We formed a group of women who live in this plot. We contribute some amount every month, after 4 months the money goes to one person. After several rounds I got my money and was able to purchase gas...It was not easy to get, at times you have not got work and therefore no money to pay to the group at the end of the month – B2-2.

I purchased gas with group money...I made gradual contributions until it totalled Ksh. 5000. It was not easy to get the monthly contribution. My husband therefore supported me, because getting the gas was a joint decision with my husband – B2-5.

They were clear on their motivations for acquiring gas, amongst them wanting to make economic savings, a direct contradiction of the narrative on extravagance.

We started by forming a women's group with various development goals. During one meeting, we said we should all move to gas because it will save us money, saves time, when child wakes to go to school it is fast, unlike the other stove which takes time. Once the savings was enough, we went as a group to the shop to buy it – B2-2.

3.5. *Belonging to a group empowers women in decision-making*

The important role of women groups in enabling acquisition of the stoves also emerges from these narratives. Not only did they provide a means for savings, but more importantly they provided women with collective power for negotiation. In this respect, a woman presenting her case for acquiring a stove would not stand out as lavish and living in a dream. The groups also empowered women with the knowledge on why such solutions are necessary. These groups are generally respected and valued by men, with some women observing that men supported them in their monthly contributions when they lagged behind. One woman reported that her husband was the one who introduced her to the group she belongs to. Groups that were particularly helpful for women were those that set the agenda of acquiring cookstoves, in comparison to ones that gave members a free choice on what to purchase with their savings. In the latter category men were still able to wield control over the expenditure as shown in the extract below.

In the group we talk as a group. But when it comes to what we do with the money in the house, then me and my husband have to decide – B1-4.

Because the group savings alone was at times not enough to purchase CCS, making it the target output made it easier to negotiate for additional contribution from the men, overcoming their inhibitions since other households would also be making such investments.

3.6. *Women have power over continued use of CCS*

Unlike the improved wood stoves that utilize the same fuel that is used on traditional stoves, transitioning to gas entails regular cost of refills. Continuing to use gas stoves after overcoming the hurdle of acquiring it did not emerge as a major challenge even when it entailed travelling long distances to obtain it. The narratives were equally split

between women paying for the refills themselves or getting support from men. Most women reported no major challenge in purchasing fuel for the stoves, even when they had to get support from the men. Because the stoves were never meant for exclusive use but for stacking with traditional stoves, the recurring fuel costs and supply challenges were reported as manageable.

There are no difficulties in refilling it (gas), you just go to refilling shops in town and pay Ksh. 1200 for the refill ... The refilling point is far, 2 km from here, I pay Ksh. 200 for transport each way ... At times there is no gas, am told to leave the cylinder come back for it the following day which is fine because I also have the traditional stove, I have not thrown it away – B2-2.

4. Discussion

This study analyzed gender differences in intra-household decision making and how they influence the acquisition of cleaner cookstoves by the households. Current research on cookstoves has focused primarily on women, and male's perspective remain unexplored. We adopted a qualitative approach with no preordained theory to allow the views of men and women, particularly men's perspective that is poorly understood, to emerge from the study.

The study shows that men are not naïve to the negative experience of cooking on traditional stoves, having been exposed to it during childhood, youth as well as during bachelorhood. However once married, this experience becomes external, and transformed to a low priority. For men, marriage represents an exit from practical engagement in cooking and cookstoves, effectively entrenching gender norms for married men relating to cooking. In contrast, women continue to live the experience, which might explain their strong desire to transform how they cook. We find men to be resigned to the way cooking is done in their households, and a desire for change is perceived negatively. On the other hand women view the goal of clean cooking as attainable and are open to various alternatives including credit facilities to attain the goal. However, the power to make the change rests with men, except for the few women who were more educated and had their independent source of income.

While these gendered differences in perception and decision-making power on spending pose a major obstacle to acquisition of CCS in the households, the added complexity of gender norms and culture that dictate decision making in households highlights how the challenge is enormous from a sectoral perspective. The contrasting views of men and women are a clear manifestation of transformation in gender dynamics that occur when new innovations are introduced to households. The CCS puts the kitchen and cooking related decisions which is traditionally a woman's domain into a man's domain; and both women and men struggle to operate under this new arrangement. Thus men, while observing that kitchen and cooking is women's domain and they have no control over those decisions found themselves in positions where they had to make decisions on cookstoves. Women in turn have to seek permission from their husbands to make kitchen related decisions, an area where traditionally they have the decision-making authority.

Although this research was not designed based on a predetermined theory, the findings reinforce theories around power relations and gender that have been extensively studied in other development sectors [56–61]. The accepted power dynamics in the family that apportion less complex decisions to women and more complex decisions to men can no longer hold when it comes to transformation of cooking systems. Failing to account for this shift in power, for instance, by targeting only women with cookstove information could explain why many CCS programs have not been successful.

For CCS programs to succeed, there is need to acknowledge the cultural transformation that accompanies these solutions, and to develop measures to support both women and men in navigating their

changing roles. Acceptance of CCS clearly requires *relatively new, complex and effortful behavioural actions to be undertaken by the cook(s), financial decision-maker(s) and other household members at an individual level* [62] as others have also observed.

While changing established gender norms is complex and outside sphere of any single sector, in this study, we identify several avenues that cookstove practitioners can exploit to improve the sector's outcomes in the immediate and near-term. First, the fact that men have personal experience with traditional cooking suggests an opportunity for building on this experience to shift their mindset on clean cooking benefits, particularly if this is done at an early age (e.g. in schools and colleges) before the issue becomes external and someone else's problem (i.e. when they are married). Secondly, there is need to identify clean cooking benefits that would appeal to men and make them central in the awareness creation and marketing. While the benefits of time savings and reduced smoke exposure may border on 'personal comfort' or social status of women and not be perceived as important, men were the key decision makers on children's education, an outcome that can be improved by clean cooking (children having meals in time and not being late for school). Bundling cookstoves with other products such as lighting that improve education outcomes could improve their appeal to men than when sold individually as cooking devices. Third, women groups emerge as empowering, particularly when they included acquisition of clean cookstoves in their agenda. Men were reported to be highly supportive of those groups, and some contributed indirectly to purchase of cookstoves through them. They thus offer a good avenue for introducing cooking solutions to households.

As with other qualitative studies, the results of this study cannot be generalised to total populations in other settings [63]. The findings are nonetheless consistent with those of other studies on gender differences in stove preferences [21,32] and those reporting women to have higher preferences for products and services that enhance welfare than men [32,64–66]. The overall recommendation of not overlooking men in cookstove promotion efforts could therefore apply to other contexts. Another limitation was the inability to prevent participants who had taken part in the interviews from interacting with those who had not. Because participants were from same households and communities, the interview questions may have been discussed at home and responses might have reflected these discussions. We however found no evidence of such response contamination. Responses obtained from FGDs conducted later were generally consistent with those obtained from the first two FGDs where participants did not have any contact prior to the interviews. The results also show commonality in responses by gender more than what we found when we analysed responses of random couples within the sample.

The current study has some key strengths. To our knowledge, it is the first study on cookstove adoption in this setting to apply GT methodology and sequential interviews to deliver a theoretical explanation of why gender plays an important role in adoption of clean cookstoves. The study is linked to a national cookstove programme that can draw upon the contextual explanations offered by the study to inform practice. Finally, the study has generated new lines of inquiry that can be pursued in future research.

5. Conclusion

In this study, we find that men have less motivation for purchasing CCS but have stronger bargaining power within the household for large expenditure items of which clean cookstoves are considered a part of. Although women are responsible for cooking and other kitchen matters, they have less control over decision-making on the purchase of CCS and lack the ability to act on their desire for those products. Cookstoves should not be perceived as isolated products and market goods, but as broad-based interventions that transform the gender power relations within households, including women's autonomy in decision-making. This in turn requires consideration of access of women and men to

economic resources and control over them, to determine who should be targeted with information and awareness creation; what financing options should be provided to tackle their high upfront cost; and what price points should be set for these products. Education and awareness on stove benefits that target both men and women can facilitate the negotiations and bargaining required in reaching the decision to adopt the CCS by households. Using women groups as an entry point for CCS interventions should also be considered.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data generated and analysed during the study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

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